

Synthesis, spectral and antimicrobial activity of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} metal complexes of 1-(1-(furan-2-yl)ethylidene)-2-((3-methyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)(phenyl)methylene)hydrazine

Devendra Kumar* and Neelam

Department of Chemistry, Institute of Basic Sciences, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar University, Khandari Campus, Agra-282 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : dev_kumar26@indiatimes.com

Manuscript received 29 December 2010, revised 20 May 2011, accepted 07 September 2011

Abstract : Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of 1-(1-(furan-2-yl)ethylidene)-2-((3-methyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)(phenyl)methylene)hydrazine have been synthesized and characterized by TLC, elemental analyses, IR, ¹H NMR, magnetic moment values, electronic spectral and thermal studies. All the synthesized compounds, viz. (3-methyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)-phenyl-methanone (2), 3-phenyl-3-(3-methyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)hydrazone (3), 1-(1-(furan-2-yl)ethylidene)-2-((3-methyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)(phenyl)methylene)hydrazine (4) and their metal complexes (5a-d) were screened for antimicrobial activities *in vitro* against gram +ve bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus*) and gram -ve bacteria (*Escherichia coli*) and two fungi *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus*. Compound (2) exhibited significant antimicrobial activity which increased in its hydrazone (3). The activity further increased in the form of its derivative (4). However, metal complexes exhibited maximum activity against both bacteria and fungi.

Keywords : Synthesis, spectral, IR, NMR, electronic spectral, TGA, hydrazone, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Over the past few decade, the synthesis of heterocyclic molecules has become one of the main areas of interest in synthetic chemistry^{1,2}. Among nitrogen-containing heterocyclic compounds, quinazolines and their derivatives are considered as important therapeutic scaffolds^{3,4}. Heterocyclic hydrazones are well known for their wide spectrum of biological activities such as antimicrobial^{5,6}, anti-inflammatory⁷, analgesic^{7,8}, antipyretic⁸, antitubercular⁹, antiHIV¹⁰, anticancerous¹¹ and antitumour¹² activity. They also play an important role in the field of bioinorganic chemistry because their biological activity increases on complexation with metal ions. A number of metal complexes of heterocyclic hydrazones have been reported as antibacterial¹³, antifungal¹⁴ and antitumor¹⁵ agents. These facts have prompted us to synthesize new hydrazone, its derivative and metal complexes to achieve their biological activity. In this research paper we have reported the synthesis and antimicrobial activity of a new heterocyclic compound (3-methyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]-oxadiazin-2-yl)-phenyl-methanone (2), 3-phenyl-3-(3-me-

thyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)hydrazone (3), 1-(1-(furan-2-yl)ethylidene)-2-((3-methyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)(phenyl)methylene)hydrazine (4) and Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} metal complexes (5a-d) according to the Scheme 1.

Results and discussion

All the compounds were colored and stable at room temperature. Heterocyclic compound, hydrazone and its derivative were soluble in ethanol and metal complexes were soluble in DMF and DMSO. Physical and analytical data of (3-methyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)phenyl-methanone, 3-phenyl-3-(3-methyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)hydrazone, 1-(1-(furan-2-yl)ethylidene)-2-((3-methyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)(phenyl)methylene)hydrazine and their metal complexes are given in Table 1. IR spectra of all compounds exhibited bands in the region 3060.7-3030.9, 1475.7-1402.0 cm⁻¹ which may be attributed due to C-H and C=C aromatic ring stretching vibrations¹⁶ respectively. In the IR spectra of compound 2 band at 1703 cm⁻¹ is attributed to >C=O

where $\text{M}^{2+} = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$

Scheme 1

stretching vibrations¹⁶. This band has disappeared in the case of compounds 3 and a new bands at 1620.0 cm^{-1} appeared which was attributed to $>\text{C}=\text{N}-$ linkage¹⁷ formed by the condensation of $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ group of compound 2 with NH_2 group of hydrazine hydrate. In the case of compound 4, a medium sharp intensity band at 1595.1 cm^{-1} was attributed due to $>\text{C}=\text{N}-\text{N}=\text{C}<$ linkage¹⁷ which may be formed by the reaction of NH_2 group

of compound 3 with $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ group of 2-acetyl furan. These bands have shifted in lower region in the case of metal complexes which suggest the participation of nitrogen atoms of $>\text{C}=\text{N}-\text{N}=\text{C}<$ linkage in the coordination with metal ion. A medium sharp intensity band in the region $1270.0\text{--}1240.2\text{ cm}^{-1}$ of C-O-N stretching vibrations has appeared in the IR spectra of compounds 2, 3 and 4. This band has shifted towards the lower frequency region in all the metal complexes indicating the involvement of oxygen atom of oxazinoline moiety in the coordination with metal ion. IR spectra of compound 4 exhibited a medium sharp intensity band in the region 1508.7 cm^{-1} due to the furan breathing vibrations¹⁸. This band has shifted towards higher frequency region by $30\text{--}40\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the case of metal complexes which suggests that the oxygen of furan ring is involved in the coordination with metal ion. IR spectra of all metal complexes exhibited two bands in the region $3407.5\text{--}3379.1$ and $880.0\text{--}843.3\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the presence of water molecule (s) in the coordination sphere. In the IR spectra of metal complexes two new bands also appeared in the region $495.4\text{--}465.0$ and $539.3\text{--}518.3\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be attributed due to the formation of new M-O and M-N bond respectively¹⁸.

^1H NMR spectral data of compounds 2, 3 and 4 exhibited two multiplets in the range $\delta 7.53\text{--}7.46$ and $6.98\text{--}6.84$ ppm which may be due to the protons of aromatic rings¹⁹. Compound 3 exhibited a singlet at $\delta 6.64$ ppm due to NH_2 proton²⁰. A singlet in the range $\delta 2.52\text{--}2.25$ ppm was appeared in the spectra of compounds 2, 3 and 4 which may be due to protons of $(\text{CH}_3\text{C}=\text{N})$ ²⁰ group. Compound 4 also exhibited a multiplet at $\delta 7.31$ ppm due to protons of furyl ring²¹.

The electronic spectra of Co^{II} complex displayed three bands at $13005, 15812, 18860\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to the transitions $^4\text{T}_{1g} \rightarrow ^4\text{T}_{2g} (F), \rightarrow ^4\text{A}_{2g} (F)$ and $\rightarrow ^4\text{T}_{1g} (P)$ respectively which suggest that Co^{II} complex has an octahedral geometry²². The magnetic moment value of Co^{II} complex was found 4.84 BM which is in close agreement with the octahedral geometry.

Ni^{II} complex exhibited three bands at $12869, 19866$ and 26324 cm^{-1} corresponding to the transitions $^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow ^2\text{T}_{2g}, ^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow ^3\text{T}_{1g}$ and $^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow ^3\text{T}_1 (P)$ respectively which was in good agreement with octahedral geometry for this

Note

Table 1. Physical properties and elemental analysis data of compounds **2**, **3**, **4** and **5a-d**

Comps.	Molecular formula	Colour	Elemental analyses (%) : Found (Calcd.)			M.p./D.t (± 2 °C)
			C	H	N	
2	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂	Shiny brown	71.04 (71.42)	4.31 (4.76)	10.98 (11.11)	92
3	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ ON ₄	Greenish black	67.27 (67.66)	5.20 (5.26)	21.50 (21.05)	110
4	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₄	Light brown	70.25 (70.39)	5.05 (5.02)	15.10 (15.64)	130
5a	[Co(C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₄).2H ₂ O](Ac) ₂	Dark brown	52.38 (52.54)	4.98 (4.90)	9.60 (9.80)	290
5b	[Ni(C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₄).2H ₂ O](Ac) ₂	Brown	52.00 (52.56)	4.69 (4.90)	9.65 (9.81)	270
5c	[Cu(C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₄).2H ₂ O](Ac) ₂	Shiny black	52.75 (52.12)	4.75 (4.86)	9.95 (9.72)	280
5d	[Zn(C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₄).2H ₂ O](Ac) ₂	Dark brown	51.15 (51.95)	4.80 (4.84)	9.00 (9.69)	275

complex²². The magnetic moment for this complex was found 3.18 BM which is very close to the value for its octahedral environment.

The electronic spectra of the Cu^{II} complex exhibited three bands at 13345, 17232 and 25121 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the transitions ²B_{1g} → ²B_{2g}, ²B_{1g} → ²A_{2g} and ²B_{1g} → ²E_{1g} which suggest distorted octahedral geometry²³ for this complex. The magnetic moment for this complex was found 1.82 BM, which is further in conformity for a distorted octahedral geometry.

Due to diamagnetic nature of Zn^{II} no significant bands were noticed in its electronic spectra.

TGA studies of all the complexes exhibited first step decomposition between 95–105 °C corresponding to the weight loss 20.05–20.42% due to removal of outer sphere

acetate ions. The second decomposition was observed between 130–220 °C corresponding to weight loss 6.02–6.23% due to the removal of two coordinated water molecules which also suggested that water molecules are present in the coordination sphere. The third decomposition was found between 280–390 °C corresponding to weight loss 36.45–36.89% due to loss of C₁₃H₁₁O and N₂ moieties. Fourth decomposition was noticed between 410–550 °C corresponding to weight loss 25.46–25.76% due to loss of remaining part of the ligand. Finally, at 580° metal-oxide residue was left.

A comparative study of MIC values (Table 2) indicated that compound **2** has significant antimicrobial activity against both bacteria and fungi, its activity increased in the form of its hydrazone (compound **3**) which further

Table 2. The Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (× 10⁻³ mol) values of compounds **2**, **3**, **4** and **5a-d**

Comps.	Bacteria		Fungi	
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>
2	99.2	99.2	99.2	99.2
3	93.9	93.9	93.9	93.9
4	34.9	34.9	34.9	69.8
5a	43.7	43.7	43.7	43.7
5b	21.9	21.9	43.8	43.8
5c	21.7	21.7	21.7	43.4
5d	43.2	43.2	43.2	43.2
Ciprofloxacin	18.85	18.85	-	-
Griseofulvin	-	-	17.7	17.7

increased in the case of derivative compound **4**. Metal complexes were found most active against both bacteria and fungi. Among the metal complexes Cu^{II} complex was found most active against both bacteria. All synthesized compounds showed less antimicrobial activity as compared to standard drug ciprofloxacin (Antibiotic drug) and griseofulvin (Antifungal drug). However, the antibacterial activity of compound **5c** was very close to the value of standard drug ciprofloxacin and antifungal activity of this compound was close to the value of griseofulvin against the *Aspergillus niger*.

Experimental

Physical and analytical data : Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. C, H and N analyses were done by using micro analyzer technique on Carbo Erba micro analyzer 1108. IR spectra were recorded in KBr in the range of $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ on Perkin-Elmer Model Rx1 spectrometer. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker Biospin spectrometer DPX-300 MHz and electronic spectra of metal complexes were recorded on Shimadzu model (UV150-150.02) spectrometer. The magnetic susceptibilities were measured at room temperature on a Gouy balance using $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as calibrant. Thermogravimetric analyses (TGA) were recorded in a static nitrogen atmosphere with heating rate of $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ using Diamond TG/DTA analyzer.

Synthesis of *N*-benzoyl acetohydroxamic acid (1) : 6.95 g (0.1 mol) finely powdered hydroxylamine hydrochloride, dissolved in 10 ml distilled water, was mixed with 15 ml aqueous solution of NaOH (4.00 g, 0.1 mol). The mixture was stirred at $0\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and 11.56 ml (0.1 mol) benzoyl chloride dissolved in 10 ml ether was added drop by drop. Then, 7.11 ml (0.1 mol) acetyl chloride dissolved in 10 ml ether was mixed slowly and stirring continued until precipitate was obtained. The precipitate was filtered and washed with cold water. The obtained product was recrystallized by ethyl acetate and dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 under reduced pressure.

Synthesis of (3-methyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)-phenyl-methanone (2) : 2.18 g (0.02 mol) *o*-aminophenol was dissolved in 20 ml absolute alcohol. To this, 3.58 g (0.02 mol) *N*-benzoyl acetohydroxamic acid, dissolved in 25 ml absolute alcohol was added and refluxed for 18 h. On cooling the contents at room tem-

perature brown colored product was obtained. The obtained product was recrystallized from ethyl alcohol and dried in a vacuum desiccator over anhydrous CaCl_2 .

Synthesis of 3-phenyl-3-(3-methyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)hydrazone (3) : 1.00 g (0.004 mol) 3-methyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl-phenyl-methanone was dissolved in 30 ml absolute alcohol and 0.20 ml (0.004 mol) hydrazine hydrate in 15 ml absolute alcohol was mixed. The mixture was refluxed for 22 h and allowed to cool at room temperature then poured onto crushed ice. The obtained brown colored product was filtered and recrystallized from ethyl alcohol. It was finally dried in a vacuum desiccator over anhydrous CaCl_2 .

Synthesis of 1-(1-(furan-2-yl)ethylidene)-2-((3-methyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)(phenyl)methylene)hydrazine (4) : 0.532 g (0.002 mol) 3-phenyl-3-(3-methyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)hydrazone was dissolved in 15 ml absolute alcohol by warming and 0.20 ml (0.002 mol) 2-acetyl furan dissolved in 10 ml absolute alcohol was mixed. The mixture was refluxed for 12 h and then allowed to cool at room temperature and poured onto the crushed ice. The obtained solid product was filtered and recrystallized from ethyl alcohol. Finally, it was dried in a vacuum desiccator over anhydrous CaCl_2 .

Synthesis of metal complexes of 1-(1-(furan-2-yl)ethylidene)-2-((3-methyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)(phenyl)methylene)hydrazine (5a-d) : 0.716 g (0.002 mol) 1-(1-(furan-2-yl)ethylidene)-2-((3-methyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)(phenyl)methylene)hydrazine dissolved in 15 ml absolute alcohol, was mixed with 10 ml aqueous solution of (0.002 mol) cobalt acetate tetrahydrate/nickel acetate tetrahydrate/copper acetate monohydrate/zinc acetate monohydrate. The contents were refluxed for 3–4 h. On cooling, precipitates were obtained which were filtered, washed with alcohol followed by ether and then dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 in a vacuum desiccator.

Antimicrobial activity : The antimicrobial studies of the synthesized compounds were screened against the bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram +ve) and *Escherichia coli* (Gram -ve) and fungi *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus* by adopting Serial Dilution Method²⁴ in suitable nutrient medium (6.0 g peptone, 3.0 g yeast extract, 1.5 g beef extract, 1.5 g agar only for slant and

1.0 g dextrose in one litre distilled water for bacteria and 10.0 g peptone, 20.5 g agar only for slant 20.0 g dextrose in one litre distilled water for fungi). Graded diluted solutions of the test compounds, with the micro organisms under examination using aseptic condition, were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h in case of bacteria and at 28 °C for 96 h in case of fungi in a B.O.D. incubator. The test tube having the highest dilution, i.e. lowest concentration showing no visible turbidity was chosen for the MIC value.

References

1. A. R. Katritzky, C. W. Rees and E. F. V. Scriven, "Comprehensive Heterocyclic Chemistry II", Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1996, Vol. 9.
2. J. A. Joule and K. Mills, "Heterocyclic Chemistry", 4th ed., Blackwell Science, Oxford, 2000.
3. V. Nagarajan, C. S. Elinor, L. Jean, G. K. John, B. N. Kevin and D. Marc, *Acta Crystallo.*, 2006, **62E**, 5003.
4. Y. Yoshihisa, O. Toyonari and I. Ichizo, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1974, **47**, 339.
5. G. R. Jani, K. B. Vyas and Z. Franco, *E-J. Chem.*, 2009, **6**, 1228.
6. Devendra Kumar, Dharmendri and Anupama Bhadauria, *J. Inst. Chemists (India)*, 2009, **81**, 161.
7. M. A. A. Radhwan, E. A. Ragab, N. M. Sabry and S. M. El-Shenawy, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2007, **15**, 3832.
8. E. V. Shchegol'kov, O. G. Khudina, L. V. Anikina, Ya. V. Burgart and V. I. Saloutin, *J. Pharm. Chem.*, 2006, **40**, 373.
9. L. Savini, L. Chiasserini, A. Gaeta and C. Pellerano, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2002, **10**, 2193.
10. P. Vicini, M. I. Incerti, P. L. Colla and R. Loddo, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2009, **44**, 1801.
11. N. Terzioglu and A. Gursoy, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2003, **38**, 781.
12. R. M. Mohareb and A. A. Mohamed, *Molecules*, 2010, **15**, 3602.
13. M. A. Affan, B. A. Fasihuddin, Y. Z. Liew, S. W. Foo and J. Ismail, *J. Sci. Res.*, 2009, **1**, 306.
14. N. H. Al-Sha'alan, *Molecules*, 2007, **12**, 1080.
15. Y. Kumar and P. D. Sethi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **67**, 796.
16. G. C. Bassler and R. M. Silverstein, "Spectroscopic Identification of Organic Compounds", 2nd ed., John Wiley & Sons Inc, New York, 1967.
17. D. H. Williams and I. Fleming, "Spectroscopic Methods in Organic Chemistry", 5th ed., Tata McGraw Hill Publishing Company Ltd., USA, 1996.
18. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 5th ed., John Wiley & Sons Inc, New York, 1997.
19. Y. R. Sharma, "Elementary Organic Spectroscopy", 12th ed., S. Chand and Company Ltd., New Delhi, 2000.
20. A. M. Awadallah and N. M. El-Halabi, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2004, **29**, 280.
21. L. M. Jackman, "Applications of Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy in Organic Chemistry", 1st ed., Pergamon, New York, 1959.
22. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.
23. A. B. P. Lever and E. Mantovani, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 40.
24. D. F. Spooner and G. Sykes, "Methods in Microbiology", Academic Press, London, 1972.

